

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FREEMAN****FIRST NAME: JAMES****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on macOS Ventura 13.0.1

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Dissertation writing must always be?

- Informal and fictional
- Impersonal and formal¹**
- Personal and Informal
- Subjective and superficial

2. What is not a component of a research argument?

- Evidence
- Purpose²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK: (PERIOD 1)*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7–12.

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago ; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 56–57.

- Claim
 - Reasons
3. To make a research argument convincing and credible, it should be able to do the following except.
- Ignore constricting and inequitable perspectives
 - Consider contradictory and complementary perspectives
 - Dismiss extrinsic and seemingly twisted perspectives³**
 - Identify and address anticipated questions and possible readers' reservations
4. To dodge what has been termed 'chronic procrastination and writer's block' in academic writing, it is expedient to
- Work under pressure⁴**
 - Start early
 - Set achievable goals
 - Use time well
5. Academic writing should be all of the following except
- Ornate⁵**
 - Concise

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK: (PERIOD 1)*, 9.

⁴ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 83.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK: (PERIOD 1)*, 7–12.

- Convincing
 - Unambiguous
6. What is the difference between academic and everyday research?
- Academic research has a standard structure, style, and content, and, unlike everyday research, it presents facts and findings without any embellishment⁶**
 - Academic research is personal, while everyday research is impersonal
 - Academic research is emotional and self-gratifying, while everyday research is rational and systematic
 - Academic research can be selective, sensual, and strategic, while everyday research is careful, casual, and wishful
7. The reliability of the sources of a book or an article can be determined by
- The reputation of the author
 - The reputation of the sponsor
 - The reputation of the publishing house
 - All of the above⁷**
8. What are the three critical components of a research argument?
- Logic, relevance, and reliability

⁶ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 19–22.

⁷ Turabian et al., 35–44.

- Claim, reasons, and evidence**⁸
- Purpose, prescription, and persuasion
- Claim, warrant, and reasons

9. Why is citation critical in academic writing?

- To maintain academic integrity
- To recognize the contribution of others
- To concede to the concept of attribution
- All of the above**⁹

10. Academic research students are expected to

- Explore and employ all data sources
- Paraphrase and summarize without attribution
- Randomly apply citation styles
- Do none of the above**¹⁰

11. When using tables and figures in research, it is ideal to place them

- Immediately after the paragraph in which they were first mentioned
- Farther along or just before the text where they were first mentioned
- In the appendix at the end of the work, if they are too large to fit into the text

⁸ Turabian et al., 56–67.

⁹ Turabian et al., 139.

¹⁰ Turabian et al., 370–71.

All of the above¹¹

12. When presenting tables and figures that I did not generate, I must acknowledge the sources

If I present them as they are

If I present the information in a new form

If I add or merge data from multiple sources by meta-analysis

All of the above¹²

13. The title of a dissertation must be

Direct

Descriptive

Simple

All of the above¹³

14. An abstract in a dissertation

Is the first numbered page

Starts with the Roman numeral iii

Is a concise synopsis of the research

¹¹ Turabian et al., 382.

¹² Turabian et al., 381–93.

¹³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 63–66.

All of the above¹⁴

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: (Period 1)*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago ; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 68.